

RISK FACTORS OF UROLITHIASIS FORMATION WITH REFERENCE TO URINE VALUES

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The incidence of renal stones varies depending on gender, age, geographic location, ethnic background and dietary differences. obesity, Hypercalciuria, hyperoxaluria, insulin resistance diabetes, and other related diseases are common risk factors for stone formation. **Materials and Methods:** A total of one hundred patients suffering from renal stone and hypertension or obesity or both of them. It was done by using reagent strips from HUMAN test (Germany), by dipping the strip in urine and compared the results with the standard. A single drop was transferred to a clean glass slide and cover slip was applied to direct microscopic examination⁽¹²⁴⁾ using HPF, OLYMPUS (Japan) microscope for examination of pus cells, erythrocytes, crystals, epithelial cells and casts. **Results:** The male group composed of 57% patients. The statistical analysis of result using T-Test shows not statistical a significant difference($P > 0.05$). the statistical

analysis of result using F-Test showed all of urine value had no statistically significant difference($P > 0.05$). **Conclusions:** Hypertension was not a significant linear or non-linear predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. Renal stone patients revealed increased cast formation compared to controls, but BMI did not significantly modulate this parameter. Crystalluria elevated in stone patients irrespective of body mass index (BMI) category.

KEYWORDS: epidemiology, urolithiasis, risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

Kidney stone disease is common disease that is estimated to produce medical cost of 2.1 billions \$ per year in United States only which affecting the population with a peak of incidence around the third to fourth decade of life.^[1] Its etiology is related to diet, increase urinary solutes and colloids in hot weather, especially excess of mucoprotein, decrease urinary citrate, urinary infection, inadequate urinary drainage, and increase serum calcium. There are many types of kidney stones, e.g. calcium oxalate, triple phosphate, uric acid, urate, cystine and xanthine stone. Some kidney stones may be presented with pain, while the others presented with hematuria, pyuria, nausea, uremia and vomiting. Obesity is now one of the most widespread medical problems. . Increasing prevalence of overweight and obesity is an important public health problem contributing to significant excess in morbidity and mortality.^[2] The risk factors of obesity are their correlation with many chronic disease like cardiovascular diseases, renal disease, and some metabolic disorder diseases like hyperlipidemia. Hypertension is a leading cause of human cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. It is very common and 25% of the population with a blood pressure above 140/90, usually symptomless, with the potential devastating effects.^[3] Despite the prevalence of hypertension and its associated complications, control of the disease is far from adequate.^[4] Many domestic and international reports have currently focused on the risk factors for renal stone formation. These diverse risk factors including age, gender, race, drugs, genetic, dietary, and environmental factors like occupation and heat exposure as well as drinking water are all reported to be associated with kidney stone prevalence.^[5,6] The incidence of renal stones varies depending on gender, age, geographic location, ethnic background and dietary differences. obesity, Hypercalciuria, hyperoxaluria, insulin resistance diabetes, and other related diseases are common risk factors for stone formation.^[7] Despite these recognized risks, it has been found that patients still have low awareness of kidney disease and its potential safety risks with communication lacking with doctors, which greatly increases the risk of disease.^[8,9] It was found that identifying the risk factors associated with renal stones can serve as a valuable reference for individuals, enabling them to implement preventive measures in their daily lives to reduce the incidence of this condition.

Patients and Methods

Patients

A total of one hundred patients suffering from renal stone and hypertension or obesity or both of them. Patients attended Urology Department in Tikrit Teaching Hospital and AL-Harery Teaching Hospital in Medical City, Baghdad.

Collection of samples

Mid-stream urine (MSU) specimens were collected in sterile screw-capped tubes after patient instructed to clean the perineum. 10-20 ml of urine were collected and transported to the laboratory within one hour.^[122]

Examination of urine using reagent strip test

This test was used for detection of leukocyte esterase enzyme, nitrate reductase, pH and protein. It was done by using reagent strips from HUMAN test (Germany), by dipping the strip in urine and compared the results with the standard.^[10]

Microscopic examination of urine specimens

Direct microscopic examination of the urine was done as the first step in the laboratory diagnosis of urinary tract infection. 10 ml quantities of clean-catch midstream urine specimen were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes using centrifuge KOKUSAN (Japan). The 9 ml supernatant was decanted and the sediment was suspended in the 1 ml remaining urine.^[124] A single drop was transferred to a clean glass slide and cover slip was applied to direct microscopic examination^[124] using HPF, OLYMPUS (Japan) microscope for examination of pus cells, erythrocytes, crystals, epithelial cells and casts. Detection of pyuria was more readily determined by finding more than 10 leukocytes of centrifuged urine.^[125] Detection of haematuria is frequently seen in acute cystitis but it is not a diagnostic for UTI.^[126]

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out following Al-Jebouri and Kaki.^[11,12]

RESULTS

Chemical analysis of urine values

The urine values like cast, crystal, pH were distributed according to sex, age, body mass index, resident, blood pressure, urinary tract infection and the pH of urine.

Sex Table 1 shows urine values of renal stone patients were distributed into two groups according gender. The male group composed of 57% patients. The statistical analysis of result using T-Test shows not statistical a significant difference ($P > 0.05$).

Regression Model For each urinary parameter was utilized with a simple linear regression as fellow

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Sex})$$

Where: Female = 0 and Male = 1

β_1 represents the effect of sex (male vs female) and the regression coefficients (β) of pH, cast and crystal for male effect of +0.14, +1.77 and +1.10 and the interpretation was slightly higher pH, higher cast and higher crystalluria in males respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Comparison of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria between male and female renal stone patients. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Independent samples t-test revealed no statistically significant differences between sexes ($P > 0.05$). on urinary pH, cast count, or crystalluria in renal stone patients.

Table 1. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patient according to gender

Variable	Male			Female			Control	t	df	P
	Mean	SD	SE	Mean	SD	SE				
pH	6.02	6.02	0.14	5.67	1.04	0.16	6	-1.61 ns	91	0.11
Cast	11.39	11.39	1.30	10.83	4.77	1.10	0	-0.32 ns	33	0.75
Crystal	9.40	9.40	0.64	9.18	4.40	0.75	0.04	-0.23 ns	70	0.82

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 1. Linear regression of urinary parameters by sex.

Age

Table 2 shows urine values of renal stone patients were distributed into three groups according ages. the statistical analysis of result using F-Test showed all of urine value had no

statistical significant difference($P > 0.05$). A simple linear regression was applied for each urinary parameter using ordered age groups

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Age Group})$$

Age coding:

20–35 years = 1

36–50 years = 2

51 years = 3.

Figure 2 shows a linear regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria across age groups in renal stone patients. Age was treated as an ordinal variable. All regression slopes (β) indicated weak negative trends with increasing age, but none reached statistical significance ($P > 0.05$). The regression trends were weak and consistent with one-way ANOVA results ($P > 0.05$ for all variables). Age was not a significant predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria in renal stone patients. Linear regression analysis revealed weak negative associations between age and urinary pH ($\beta = -0.03$), cast count ($\beta = -0.91$), and crystalluria ($\beta = -0.38$). However, none of these associations were statistically significant, indicating that age did not independently influence urinary parameters in renal stone patients.

Table 2. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patient according to age

variable	20-35years			36-50years			>51years			Control	f	p
	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE			
pH	5.815	1.22	0.26	6.027	0.986	0.162	5.75	1.056	0.167	6	0.68 ^{NS}	0.511
cast	12.6	6.066	2.71	11	5.745	1.59	10.78	4.672	1.1	0	0.24 ^{NS}	0.789
crystal	10.278	3.23	0.76	8.562	4.586	0.84	9.516	4.668	0.838	0.04	0.95 ^{NS}	0.392

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 2. Linear regression of urinary parameters by age groups.

Residence

Table 3 shows urine values of renal stone patients distributed into two groups according to residence. The urban group composed of 78% of patients. The statistical analysis of result using T-Test shows all of urine value had no statistical a significant difference($P > 0.05$). Figure 3 shows Polynomial regression visualization of urinary parameters by residence (rural vs urban). No meaningful non-linear association was observed, consistent with non-significant t-test results ($P > 0.05$). Non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis demonstrated weak curvilinear trends between age and urinary parameters; however, these associations were not statistically significant. Residence showed no meaningful linear or non-linear relationship with urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria.

Table 3. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patients according to residence.

Variable	Rural			Urban			Control	t	df	p
	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE				
pH	5.86	1.32	0.28	5.87	0.99	0.11	6	-0.02 ^{Ns}	28	0.98
cast	11.31	5.76	1.6	11	4.9	1	0	0.16 ^{Ns}	21	0.87
crystal	9.17	4.45	1	9.35	4.37	0.55	0.04	-0.15 ^{Ns}	27	0.88

*,significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 3. Non-linear regression of urinary parameters by residence

Blood pressure

Table 4 shows urine values of renal stone patients distributed into two groups according to blood pressure. The statistical analysis of result using T-test revealed all of urine values were statistically not a significant ($P > 0.05$). Hypertension was not a significant linear or non-linear predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. Figure 4 shows a non-linear

(quadratic) regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria according to hypertension condition . Although mild curvilinear trends were observed for casts and crystals but no statistically significant association was detected ($P > 0.05$). Quadratic regression analysis demonstrated weak non-linear trends between hypertension status and urinary cast and crystal values. These associations were not statistically significant. Urinary pH remained stable across groups indicating no effect of hypertension on urinary biochemical parameters.

Table 4. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patients according to blood pressure.

Variable	Hypertensive			Non-hypertensive			Control	t	df	p
	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE				
pH	5.8	0.926	0.14	5.9	1.18	0.16	6	-0.38 ^{Ns}	96	0.71
cast	10	4.58	1.1	12	5.57	4.58	0	-1.31 ^{Ns}	32	0.20
crystal	9.42	4.11	0.68	9.22	4.59	4.11	0.04	0.20 ^{Ns}	77	0.84

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 4. Non-linear regression of urinary parameters by hypertension status.

Urinary tract infection(UTI)

Table 5 shows urine values of renal stone patients were distributed into two groups according to incidence of UTI. The infected group included 9% of patients(i.e. with UTI). The statistical analysis of result utilizing T-test shows all of urine values were statistically not significant ($P > 0.05$). A simple linear regression was applied for each urinary parameter:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Infection Status})$$

Coding used

0 = Control, 1 = Non-infected, 2 = Infected

Here, β_1 represents the linear change in the urinary parameter with increasing infection status. Figure 5 shows linear regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria according to infection situation. Infection status was treated as an ordinal variable for visualization purposes. Although positive slopes were observed for casts and crystals, no statistically significant associations were traced ($P > 0.05$).

Table 5. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patients according to combined of urinary tract infection (UTI).

variable	Infected			Non- infected			Control	t	df	p
	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE				
pH	5.89	0.333	0.11	5.87	1.11	0.12		0.14 ^{NS}	32	0.89
cast	11.4	5.81	2.6	11.06	5.14	0.92		0.12 ^{NS}	5	0.91
crystal	8	3.46	1.2	9.47	4.45	0.52		-1.16 ^{NS}	11	0.27

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 5. Linear regression of urinary parameters by infection status.

pH

Table 6 shows urine values of renal stone patients were distributed into three groups according to pH of urine. The statistical analysis of result using F-test showed significant difference ($P < 0.05$) of increasing in urine cast. Other values did not show any significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Figure 6 Non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis of urinary cast and crystal values across urinary pH categories of kidney stone patients. Cast formation demonstrated a significant inverted-U relationship with urinary pH, peaking at pH 6–7 (ANOVA, $P < 0.05$), whereas crystalluria did not show a non-significant declining trend with increasing pH. One-way ANOVA demonstrated a significant impact on urinary pH on cast formation ($F = 3.57$, $P = 0.039$). Quadratic regression statistics revealed an inverted-U

relationship, with maximal cast values at pH 6–7. In contrast, crystalluria showed a declining but statistically non-significant trend across pH categories ($P > 0.05$).

Table 6. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patients according to urine pH of renal stone patient

variable	4-5pH			6-7 pH			8-9 pH			Control	f	p
	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE	mean	SD	SE			
cast	8.333b	2.236	0.745	12.82a	5.746	1.22	8.6b	2.702	1.21	0	3.57*	0.039
crystal	10a	4.578	0.898	9.2a	4.388	0.654	8a	3.621	1.15	0.04	0.79 ^{NS}	0.458

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 6. Non-linear regression of casts and crystals by urinary pH.

Body mass index (BMI)

Table 7 shows urine values of renal stone patients were gathered into four groups according to BMI. The statistical analysis of result using F-test shows all of urine values were statistically not significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The descriptive statistical analysis found out that pH values were relatively stable with reference to BMI groups (5,25-5.97) but slight decrease was seen in the $\geq 40\text{kg/m}^2$ group. Urinary pH did not show a clinically meaningful variation with body mass index. Renal stone patients revealed increased cast formation compared to controls, but BMI did not significantly modulate this parameter. Crystalluria elevated in stone patients irrespective of body mass index (BMI) category (Figure 7). Figure 7 shows non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria across body mass index categories in renal stone patients. All parameters demonstrated inverted-U trends with peak values in overweight individuals; however, no statistically significant associations were observed (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$). Quadratic regression analysis showed mild non-linear relationships between BMI and urinary parameters, with peak cast

and crystal values observed in overweight patients. However, one-way ANOVA showed no statistically significant differences among BMI categories ($P > 0.05$), indicating that BMI did not independently influence urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria.

Table 7. Distribution of urine values of renal stone patients according to body mass index.

variable	18-24 Kg/m ²		25-29.9 Kg/m ²		+30 Kg/m ²		+40 Kg/m ²		Control	F	p
	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD	mean	SD			
pH	5.86a	1.066	5.97a	1.124	5.89a	1.03	5.25a	0.957	6	0.56 ^{NS}	0.642
cast	11.11a	5.14	12.7a	6.36	10.56a	4.68	9a	1	0	0.59 ^{NS}	0.624
crystal	9.309a	4.35	10.48a	4.47	8.76a	4.36	7a	3	0.04	1.14 ^{NS}	0.334

*, significant ($P < 0.05$); **, highly significant ($P < 0.01$); NS, not significant ($P > 0.05$)

Figure 7. Non-linear regression of urinary parameters by body mass index(BMI).

DISCUSSION

The present study showed that urine values of renal stone patients were distributed into two groups according gender. The male group composed of 57% patients. The statistical analysis of result using T-Test did not reveal statistical a significant difference ($P > 0.05$). The other findings suggested that women with kidney stones experience lower health-related quality of life (HRQOL) compared with men, even accounting for clinical and demographic factors.^[13] The present study did not show that age as a significant predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria in renal stone patients, and none of the data associations were statistically significant, indicating that age did not independently influence urinary parameters in renal stone patients.^[14,15] Furthermore, sex and age are independently associated with urine values and kidney stone risk. Male and younger patients are usually exhibit diet-driven abnormalities, whereas females and older patients present with risks linked to intrinsic physiology. The demographic characteristics findings enhance the understanding of patient-specific stone risk and support tailored approaches to evaluation and

consequently prevention.^[16,17,18] In a study carried out elsewhere which soke to provide a thorough assessment of the estimated burden and trends related to kidney stones among people aged 20–54 at the national, regional, and worldwide levels from 1990 to 2021 using data from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 202.^[19] It was found that working-age persons revealed a significantly higher frequency of stone disease, while older populations have a lower incidence.^[19,20,21,22] On the other hand, in France, the highest prevalence of urolithiasis was seen in women aged between 30 to 39 years old, whereas the highest incidence occurred in men aged 40 to 49 years. The overall male-to-female (M/F) ratio was 2.28.^[20] Furthermore, in Germany, a study utilized interviews, the prevalence of urolithiasis was 9.7% in males and 5.9% in women over the age of 5.^[19,23] In comparison, a cohort study in Korea found out that the highest incidence of urolithiasis occurred at ages 50 to 54 years for men and 55 to 59 years for women.^[24] Multiple studies demonstrated that the occurrence of stones has increased significantly among both men and women aged 25 and up, with men showing a particularly noticeable tendency. Furthermore, a study of the age distribution of stone patients between 1979 and 2001 showed that the observed rise in prevalence and frequency was primarily due to the occurrence of stones in the older age group of >50 years. In contrast, there was also evidence indicating that an increasing number of young women were affected by urinary renal stone.^[23,25] The present study revealed that urine values of renal stone patients distributed into two groups according to residence. The urban group composed of 78% of patients. The statistical analysis of result using T-Test showed all of urine values had no statistical significant differences ($P > 0.05$). The present study also showed a Polynomial regression visualization of urinary parameters by residence (rural vs urban). No meaningful non-linear association was observed, consistent with non-significant t-test results ($P > 0.05$). Non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis demonstrated weak curvilinear trends between age and urinary parameters; however, these associations were not statistically significant. Residence showed no meaningful linear or non-linear relationship with urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. However, the data on distribution of urolithiasis are lacking in China. But later the Chinese researchers gathered a total of 1,169,651 urban inhabitants across China in 2008 to detect if they are experiencing kidney stones by ultrasound diagnosis. The overall prevalence rate was estimated to be 4.0 %, 4.8 % in men and 3.0 % in women. Urolithiasis was predominant among males and was found in all age groups. The prevalence in the north was 4.1 % which was slightly higher than that in the south which showed 4.0 %. The Chinese study provided a quantitative and updated estimate of the renal stone prevalence in a nationally representative sample.^[19,26] The data presented

here revealed that a non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria according to hypertension condition. Although mild curvilinear trends were observed for casts and crystals but no statistically significant association was detected ($P > 0.05$). Quadratic regression analysis demonstrated weak non-linear trends between hypertension status and urinary cast and crystal values. These associations were not statistically significant. Urinary pH remained stable across groups indicating no effect of hypertension on urinary biochemical parameters. The science of epidemiology of urolithiasis advanced and better understanding of this disease achieved. Urolithiasis is frequently associated with systemic disorders such as metabolic syndrome, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, obesity, and chronic kidney disease, which can both predispose to kidney stone formation, and occur as sequelae of nephrolithiasis.^[17] The descriptive statistical analysis found out that pH values were relatively stable with reference to BMI groups.^[27,28] but slight decrease was seen in the $\geq 40\text{kg/m}^2$ group. Urinary pH did not show a clinically meaningful variation with body mass index. Renal stone patients revealed increased cast formation compared to controls, but BMI did not significantly modulate this parameter. Crystalluria elevated in stone patients irrespective of body mass index (BMI) category. The present study showed non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria across body mass index categories in renal stone patients. All parameters demonstrated inverted-U trends with peak values in overweight individuals. However, no statistically significant associations were observed (ANOVA, $P > 0.05$). Quadratic regression analysis showed mild non-linear relationships between BMI and urinary parameters, with peak cast and crystal values observed in overweight patients. However, one-way ANOVA showed no statistically significant differences among BMI categories ($P > 0.05$), indicating that BMI did not independently influence urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. Furthermore, although the precise mechanisms linking obesity to kidney stone formation remain unclear, it was found out that obesity is associated with insulin resistance, and compensatory hyperinsulinemia, metabolic disturbances that may promote the development of calcium-based stones. In addition, increased body mass can lead to higher urinary excretion of uric acid, and oxalate, both of which are established risk factors for calcium oxalate stone formation.^[29] A cross sectional, and longitudinal cohort study identified the association between KSD and eight different obesity related indices found all indices to be significantly associated with increased risk of disease, with 10.95 of males and 4.0% of females affected with the diseases.^[30] Certain bariatric surgeries such as the Roux En Y gastric bypass is also associated with an increase in stone burden.^[31] Hypertension was not a

significant linear or non-linear predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. The data presented here showed a non-linear (quadratic) regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria according to hypertension condition. Although mild curvilinear trends were observed for casts and crystals but no statistically significant association was detected ($P > 0.05$). Quadratic regression analysis demonstrated weak non-linear trends between hypertension status and urinary cast and crystal values. These associations were not statistically significant. Urinary pH remained stable across groups indicating no effect of hypertension on urinary biochemical parameters. Contemporary studies confirmed that stone formers are more likely to develop hypertension, although evidence regarding the reciprocal risk of nephrolithiasis in hypertensive patients remains variable.^[32,33] An increased urinary calcium excretion, commonly seen in patients with hypertension, may underlie the observed relationship between hypertension and kidney stone formation.^[34] The presence of symptomatic kidney stones increases the likelihood of chronic, and end-stage renal disease (ESRD), independent of established cardiovascular risk factors, with attributable risk of ESRD from symptomatic urolithiasis being approximately 5.1%.^[51] Although nephrolithiasis is rarely the primary driver of ESRD, it remains an important contributing factor. The development of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in the context of kidney stones is primarily attributed to obstructive uropathy, or pyelonephritis. However, the present study showed that linear regression analysis of urinary pH, cast count, and crystalluria according to infection situation. Infection status was treated as an ordinal variable for visualization purposes. Although positive slopes were observed for casts and crystals, no statistically significant associations were traced ($P > 0.05$). Additional mechanisms such as crystal deposition in the ducts of Bellini, and parenchymal injury from shockwave lithotripsy, may also play a role. Among individuals with nephrolithiasis, those at highest risk for CKD include patients with rare hereditary disorders, (such as cystinuria, primary hyperoxaluria), hypertension, recurrent urinary tract infections (rUTIs), diabetes and struvite stones.^[51] CKD, and ESRD patients are commonly comorbid with other serious ailments, overshadowing the effects of kidney stones, complicating the assessment of nephrolithiasis as a contributing factor. Either way, preserving renal function should thus be a key priority in healthcare, to reduce associated morbidity and mortality.

CONCLUSIONS

Hypertension was not a significant linear or non-linear predictor of urinary pH, cast formation, or crystalluria. Renal stone patients revealed increased cast formation compared to

controls, but BMI did not significantly modulate this parameter. Crystalluria elevated in stone patients irrespective of body mass index (BMI) category.

Statement of Ethics

All the procedures involving human participation were conducted in strict accordance with ethical standards of Institutional Research Committee, Department of Scientific Research, Tikrit University as well as the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its subsequent amendments or equivalent ethical norms.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise.

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